

PHTHALONITRILE MODIFIED MULTI-HYDROXYL PHENOLIC: SYNTHESIS, CURING AND PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

In order to improve the processability and thermal stability of addition-curable phenolic resin, multi-hydroxyl phenolic with different phthalonitrile substitution degree was prepared. The chemical structure, curing behaviour, processability and thermal stability were studied. The curing temperature of HPPh2 was 259 °C while that of LPPh2 was 338 °C, as the result of different residual hydroxyl group contents. The rheological tests demonstrated that the processing window of LPPh2 was as wide as 155 °C while that of HPPh2 was only 75 °C. TG tests showed that the char yield at 800 °C of LPPh2 was as high as 76% due to the low residual hydroxyl contents after curing. The correlation between the phthalonitrile contents, hydroxyl contents and the properties of the resin was established, which is meaningful for the molecular design.

1 INTRODUCTION

Phenolic, as one of the most important heat-resistant polymer, exhibited high char yield and decomposition temperature [1, 2]. However, it also suffers from the release of volatiles during curing. Much efforts have been devoted to obtaining addition-cure phenolic resins. Allyl, propargyl and benzoxazine groups were introduced into the phenolic backbone to transfer the curing mechanism from condensation to addition [3-5]. With the rapid development of electronics, the demand for heat-resistant polymers was raised to a higher level. Phthalonitrile resins have attracted more attention lately owing to high glass transition temperature and outstanding thermal performance with no volatile releasing, as the result of aromatic structure and heterocyclic crosslinking network [6, 7]. The incorporation of phthalonitrile moieties into phenolic backbone was proved to be an efficient method to improve the thermal stability. However, phthalonitrile modified phenolic also suffers from the high curing temperature and poor processability [8, 9]. It was proved that hydroxyl and amine could trigger the curing reaction of phthalonitrile moieties. Besides, increasing the backbone length or introducing soft moieties, such as ether, alkyl chain or allyl, are beneficial to the molecular chain movement, thus improving the processability of the resin [10-12].

In order to investigate the effect of phthalonitrile and hydroxyl group contents on the polymer properties, multi-hydroxyl phenolic was synthesized with hydroquinone and formaldehyde in this paper. Novel resins with different phthalonitrile substitution degree were obtained and the properties were evaluated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Materials

Formaldehyde solution, with the solid content of 37 wt%, was supplied by Beijing Chemical Works. Hydroquinone was provided by Beijing Chemical Works. Phenol was purchased from Yongda Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd. The catalyst, oxalic acid was provided by Beijing Chemical Works, and potassium carbonate was supplied by Hebei Xinji Chemical Group Co., Ltd. The solvent, butanone and N, N-dimethylformamide (DMF) were purchased from Beijing Chemical Works. All chemical reagents were of analytical grade and used as received unless otherwise stated.

2.2 Synthesis of LPh and HPh

Phenol(37.61 g), hydroquinone(22 g) and formaldehyde solution(32.45 g) were mixed in a three-necked flask first and the solution was heated to 68 °C, followed by adding oxalic acid(0.38 g). After the reaction at 90 °C for 2 h, brown viscous liquid was obtained. The product of HPh was collected after removing the solvent by reduced pressure distillation and drying in a vacuum oven.

LPh was synthesized following the similar procedure. The amount of phenol changed to 56.41 g without adding hydroquinone.

2.3 Synthesis of HPPh1, HPPh2 and LPPh2

HPh(11.02 g) was dissolved in N,N-dimethylformamide(67.57 g) first, then the catalyst, K₂CO₃ (63.02 g, 0.45 mol) and 4-nitrophthalonitrile(57.94 g, 0.33 mol) was added to the solution. After heating at 80 °C for 8 h in nitrogen atmosphere, brown solution was obtained. HPPh1 product was collected by filtering, rotary evaporation and repeatedly washing with distilled water until neutral. The solvent was removed in vacuum at 120 °C.

HPPh2 was synthesized following the similar procedure. The amount of HPh, K₂CO₃ and 4-nitrophthalonitrile was 11.18 g, 20.7 g and 12.98 g, respectively.

LPPh2 was synthesized following the similar procedure. HPh was replaced with LPh and the amount of LPh, K₂CO₃ and 4-nitrophthalonitrile was 10.7 g, 20.7 g and 12.98 g, respectively.

2.4 Curing schedule

The curing schedule of HPPh1, HPPh2 and LPPh2 was set as 180 °C for 1 h, 230 °C for 2 h, 250 °C for 3 h and 315 °C for 2 h.

2.5 Characterization

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) spectra were recorded in the range of 4000-400 cm⁻¹ on a Bruker Tensor-27 spectrometer using KBr pellets. Solution ¹H NMR was performed on a Bruker Avance III 400 HD nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectrometer using DMSO-d₆ as solvent. Elemental analysis was carried out using a Thermo Finnigan Flash EA 1112 instrument. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was measured on Mettler DSC822e from 25 °C to 400 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹. The rheological test was performed on a TA Advanced Rheometer 2000 using 25 mm-diameter parallel plates. Thermal stability of the cured resin was investigated with a Netzsch STA 409 PC TGA machine from room temperature to 1050 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ in nitrogen atmosphere with a flow rate of 50 ml min⁻¹.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Two types of multi-hydroxyl phenolic were synthesized by adjusting the ratio among phenol, hydroquinone and formaldehyde, as Figure 1 shows. Compared to HPh, LPh has less hydroxyl groups, due to the missing of hydroquinone. After the nucleation reaction between phenolic and 4-nitrophthalonitrile, the substitution degree of phthalonitriles for LPPh2 and HPPh2 was the same, higher than that of HPPh1.

Figure 1: The synthesis scheme of HPPh1, HPPh2 and LPPh2

In order to characterize the different chemical structure of phenolic, ^1H NMR was performed. As can be seen from Figure 2, the spectra of LPh and HPh were similar, where the resonance peaks between 3.5 and 4 ppm were ascribed to the hydrogen atoms of the methylene in the phenolic backbone. The hydrogen atoms in the benzene ring resulted in the peaks between 6.5 and 7 ppm and the resonance peaks between 8.5 to 9.5 ppm were owing to the activated hydrogen in the hydroxyl groups. Element analysis was carried out to characterize the carbon and oxygen contents. The O/C ratio of LPh was 0.14 while that of HPh was as high as 0.22, which proved that the hydroxyl contents of HPh was higher than that of LPh.

Figure 2: The ^1H NMR spectra of LPh and HPh

Sample	Element	contents (wt%)	contents (mol%)
LPh	C	77.82	48.69
	H	5.81	43.62
	O	16.37	6.88
HPh	C	73.00	46.67
	H	5.62	43.08
	O	21.39	10.25

Table 1 : the elemental analysis results of LPh and HPh

The chemical structure of LPPh and HPPh was elucidated by FT-IR. After the introduction of phthalonitrile groups, as Figure 3 shows, the absorption band around 3400 cm^{-1} was owing to hydroxyl groups. The peak at 2233 cm^{-1} was due to the stretching of cyano moieties, indicating the esterification reaction between the hydroxyl and 4-nitrophthalonitrile.

Figure 3: FT-IR spectra of HPPh1, HPPh2 and LPPh2

The curing of LPPh and HPPh was self-catalyzed, as Figure 4 shows, and the crosslinking network was built by the cyano groups triggered by the residual hydroxyl. With the same phthalonitrile substitution degree, the curing temperature of HPPh2 was 259 °C while that of LPPh2 was 338 °C, as the result of different residual hydroxyl group contents. This is also proved by the curing temperature difference between HPPh1 and HPPh2 with the same multi-hydroxyl phenolic backbone. HPPh1 exhibited lower curing temperature of 238 °C compared to HPPh2. The existence of hydroxyl groups could not only promote the crosslinking reaction, but also improve the molecular chain movement, which is crucial for the crosslinking network establishment.

Figure 4: DSC curves of HPPh1, HPPh2 and LPPh2

In order to characterize the processability, rheological tests were performed. As Figure 5 shows, the processing window of LPPh2 was as wide as 155 °C while that of HPPh2 was only 75 °C. With high hydroxyl contents, it is easier to trigger the curing reaction of cyano groups, leading to shorter gelation time. At 170 °C, the gelation time for LPPh2 was about 60 min while that of HPPh2 was around 45 min. In contrast, when HPPh1 was heated to 170 °C, the gelation reaction occurred immediately as the result of high hydroxyl contents.

Figure 5: Complex viscosity of HPPh1, HPPh2 and LPPh2 as a function of temperature

As can be seen from Figure 6, the $T_{5\%}$ and $T_{10\%}$ of HPPh2 and LPPh2 was close, which was 490 and 550 °C, respectively, but the char yield at 800 °C of LPPh2 was slightly higher than that of HPPh2, as the result of relatively low residual hydroxyl group contents, which is harmful for the thermal stability. In contrast, the $T_{5\%}$ and $T_{10\%}$ of HPPh1 decreased by 20-30 °C and the char yield at 800 °C was only 71%. This is the result of low phthalonitrile substitution degree, thus the ratio of thermal stable heterocyclic and aromatic structure decreased, leading to the deterioration of thermal stability.

Figure 6: TG curves of HPPh1, HPPh2 and LPPh2

4 CONCLUSIONS

Multi-hydroxyl phenolic with different phthalonitrile substitution degree was prepared and the chemical structure, curing behavior, processability and thermal stability were studied. It was proved that the introduction of phthalonitrile could improve the initial decomposition temperature and the hydroxyl groups are beneficial to the curing temperature decrease and processability enhancement.

REFERENCES

- [1] Wang S, Wang Y, Bian C, et al. The thermal stability and pyrolysis mechanism of boron-containing phenolic resins: the effect of phenyl borates on the char formation. *Applied Surface Science*. 2015, 331: 519-529.
- [2] Wu Y, Li L, Feng S, et al. Hybrid nanocomposites based on novolac resin and octa (phenethyl) polyhedral oligomeric silsesquioxanes (POSS): miscibility, specific interactions and thermomechanical properties. *Polymer bulletin*. 2013, 70(12): 3261-3277.
- [3] Nair C R. Advances in addition-cure phenolic resins. *Progress in Polymer Science*. 2004, 29(5): 401-498.
- [4] Culbertson B M, Tiba O, Deviney M L. Bisoxazoline-phenolic resins: new thermosetting poly (amide-ether) materials for improved performance composites. 1988.
- [5] Xu S, Han Y, Guo Y, et al. Allyl Phenolic-Phthalonitrile Resins with Tunable Properties: Curing, Processability and Thermal Stability. *European Polymer Journal*, 2017, 95: 394-405.

- [6] Keller T M. Phthalonitrile-based high temperature resin. *Journal of Polymer Science Part A: Polymer Chemistry*. 1988, 26(12): 3199-3212.
- [7] Keller T M, Dominguez D D, Laskoski M. Oligomeric bisphenol A-based PEEK-like phthalonitrile-cure and polymer properties. *Journal of Polymer Science Part A: Polymer Chemistry*. 2016, 54(23): 3769-3777.
- [8] Augustine D, Mathew D, Nair C P. Phenol-containing phthalonitrile polymers-synthesis, cure characteristics and laminate properties. *Polymer International*. 2013, 62(7): 1068-1076.
- [9] Laskoski M, Neal A, Keller T M, et al. Improved synthesis of oligomeric phthalonitriles and studies designed for low temperature cure. *Journal of Polymer Science Part A: Polymer Chemistry*. 2014, 52(12): 1662-1668.
- [10] Laskoski M, Neal A, Schear M B, et al. Oligomeric aliphatic–aromatic ether containing phthalonitrile resins[J]. *Journal of Polymer Science Part A: Polymer Chemistry*. 2015, 53(18): 2186-2191.
- [11] Laskoski M, Dominguez D D, Keller T M. Alkyne-containing phthalonitrile resins: Controlling mechanical properties by selective curing. *Journal of Polymer Science Part A: Polymer Chemistry*. 2013, 51(22): 4774-4778.
- [12] Sheng H, Peng X, Guo H, et al. Synthesis and thermal properties of a novel high temperature alkyl-center-trisphenolic-based phthalonitrile polymer. *Materials Chemistry and Physics*. 2013, 142(2): 740-747.